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Application of Tracers in the Evaluation of Seepage Characteristic of Limestone - A case study of Sardar Sarovar (Narmada) Dam, Gujarat, India

Indra Prakash^{1*} and Binh Thai Pham²

¹DDG (R) Geological Survey of India, Gandhinagar, Gujarat, India

²University of Transport and Technology, Hanoi, Vietnam

ABSTRACT

This paper describes an approach to estimate seepage characteristics of limestone rocks occurring at the dam base and in the vicinity of Sardar Sarovar (Narmada) dam, Gujarat, India. The approach has three components: (1) characterization of the rock mass considering joints/ fracture system, (2) determination of chemical composition of limestone, and (3) evaluation of seepage characteristic of limestone rocks using tracer studies. Excessive seepage through foundation rocks may lead to leakage and thus can cause failure of the dam. Therefore, detailed geological and geo-hydrological investigations are required at dam site to know the surface and sub-surface geology and hydrology. Evaluation of seepage characteristics of the rocks present at the dam base and in the reservoir are required to be evaluated for tracing seepage path of sub-surface water through foundation rocks from upstream to downstream and also velocity of sub-surface water under different reservoir levels.

The study area is dominated by sub-horizontally disposed basalt flows underlain by sedimentary rocks (sandstone, shale and limestone) dissected by faults, shears and joints. Faults in the area have brought limestone rocks on the surface in the reservoir and at juxtaposition with the basalt flows in the dam foundation. The area is tectonically disturbed. Surface and sub-surface exploration revealed presence of open joints/ fractures, bedding shears traversing rocks. Limestone rocks are generally considered permeable due to presence of joints, fractures, solution channels and cavities. Chemical analysis of limestone indicated it is mostly of siliceous nature. However, at some places cavities were apprehended due to slippage of drilling rods during sub-surface exploration. Therefore, to investigate continuity of permeable zones from upstream of the dam to downstream, tracer studies were conducted using Sodium Fluorescein and Tritium.

The knowledge of hydraulic and transport characteristics of rocks is required to be assessed to improve prediction of the rate and direction of movement of seepage water through foundation. The present approach of evaluating seepage through limestone rock can also be applied in other areas for tracing groundwater movement and contamination.

Key Words: Seepage, Groundwater, tracers, Sodium Fluorescein, Tritium, limestone, dam base

*Corresponding Author

1. Introduction

Tracer tests are required to be conducted by following three components of approach: (1) characterization of the hydrogeologic framework of sub-surface water flow within the rock mass, (2) estimation of the distribution of hydraulic properties (hydraulic conductivity and storage coefficient) within that frame work, and (3) estimation of transport properties (effective porosity and dispersivity).

In the designing of the dam, it is desirable to assess seepage characteristics of the dam foundations from the economic and safety considerations. Heavy seepage through dam foundation after filling of the reservoir may lead to water storage loss and also even dam failure due to piping of the erodible material of foundation. Therefore, hydraulic properties of rocks are required to be evaluated for the estimation of sub-surface flow rates and directions and in the prediction of the movement of sub-surface water in fractured and cavernous rocks. This paper describes tracer studies carried out at Sardar Sarovar (Narmada) Project, Gujarat, India to evaluate seepage characteristics of limestone rocks occurring in the foundation and vicinity of dam.

Tracers are useful in hydrology and hydrological research [1,2] as they help in quantifying transport processes [3,4]. They provide information of flow direction and velocity as well as potential contaminant transportation and also help in determining hydraulic conductivity [5], porosity, dispersivity [6] and other hydrogeological parameters. The selection of tracers is a critical component in the design of tests. Using tracers with appropriate properties can help identify dominant transport mechanisms. Ideally, one of the tracers should move at the same velocity as the water. This tracer should be chemically inert during the course of the tracer test. That is, it should not decay, adsorb onto the rock, or react with other tracers. However, if diffusion into stagnant water or rock matrix occurs, even a chemically inert tracer will show an apparent retardation. In this regard, using several inert tracers with different coefficients of molecular diffusion can help quantify this effect. Adsorptive tracers can be used to investigate the sorptive properties of the fracture surfaces and rock matrix. Most common artificial tracers are salts and dyes [1], whereas, fluorescent tracers (dyes) are more important because of their easy handling, simple analysis, high sensitivity and low detection limit [7].

Radioactive isotopes such as Tritium are also used for tracing ground water movement and contamination. Tritium is the radioactive isotope of hydrogen. It has different attributes that make it distinctive among environmental tracers of groundwater pollution. It does not interact with the aquifer materials during movement through the porous media and is considered conservative geochemically; its activity in water sample can be measured at low level through electrolytic enrichment prior to quantification [8].

In the present study Sodium Fluorescein ($C_{20}H_{10}Na_2O_5$) and Tritium (3H) tracers were injected in the drill holes drilled in the upstream and their concentration was measured in the downstream of dam in exploratory holes to evaluate seepage of limestone rock occurring in the foundation and reservoir of Narmada dam.

2. Geotechnical Setting of the Study Area

The study area is Sardar Sarovar (Narmada) dam site, in lower Narmada valley in Rajpipla District, Gujarat India. The Narmada is the longest west flowing river in India. It is the fifth largest river in the country and the largest one in Gujarat. The Narmada dam (21°51' N; 73°45' E) is a multi-purpose concrete gravity dam creating a terminal reservoir on the Narmada River in Rajpipla district, Gujarat, India. The main dam is 1227m long and 162.5m high from the deepest foundation level.

The dam site is occupied by the “Aa” type Deccan basalt flows underlain by sedimentary rocks of Bagh beds (infra-trappeans) (Fig 1) (Table 1). Bagh beds are exposed in the upstream and downstream of the dam as inliers in the basalt and in the dam foundation at depth by faults. These rocks are occurring on the surface as inliers in the basalt. The Bagh beds are comprising of quartzitic sandstone, argillaceous sandstone, shale, pebbly sandstone and limestone are sub-horizontally disposed. The lower part of the Bagh beds is arenaceous and upper part of the beds is mainly calcareous [9]. Limestone occurring in the area is composed mainly of calcium carbonate with high content of impurities like silica (siliceous) (average SiO₂ 20%), dolomite and clay (argillaceous) in varied proportion.

Figure 1. Geology of The Sardar Sarovar (Narmada) Dam

Table 1. Stratigraphic Succession in The Lower Narmada Valley of Gujarat

Age	Formation	Description
Sub Recent to Recent		Calc tufa, soil, alluvium and gravel
Upper Cretaceous to Eocene	Deccan trap	Basalt flows intruded by dykes and sill
-----	Unconformity-----	-----
----	-----	
Middle to Upper Cretaceous	Bagh beds (Infra-trappeans)	Sandstone, Shale and Limestone.

The Narmada Valley is geologically complex and structurally disturbed [10]. The area exhibits faulted block topography with alternate ridges and valleys aligned almost in ENE-WSW direction. Tectonic imprints of both the Narmada (ENE-WSW) and West Coast (N-S to N10°E- S10°W) lineament trends are seen in this area. Distinct phases of post Deccan trap tensional and compressional deformations are seen in the 'SONATA' zone and adjoining region. These are evident from the occurrence of dyke swarms, displacement of dykes, dipping of the basalt flows and emergence of the Bagh beds from underneath the Deccan traps in juxtaposition with basalt. A number of reverse faults have been observed in the area including Narmada Main River channel fault indicating compressive post Deccan trap activity (Fig 2). The area is still under compression due to northward movement of the Indian plate. It is evident from the recent seismic activity in the NSL zone [15-18].

Figure 2. Geological Cross-Section of Dam Showing Sedimentary Rocks in Juxtaposition with Basalt Along River Channel Fault

Detailed construction stage geotechnical investigations of dam revealed weak geological layers/ features in the Deccan basalt flows including tuff, agglomerate, red bole, highly jointed zones, shears and faults. Weak sheared argillaceous sandstone layers (Infratrappean Bagh beds) also occur in juxtaposition with basalt at shallow depth in the foundation of dam. Sheared contacts of rocks posed problems of seepage and sliding of dam blocks. However, presence of dolerite dykes in the foundation rocks may resist sliding and act as cutoff for the seepage path but there is possibility of by passing the sub-surface water through dykes. Therefore, Seepage characteristics of the limestone was investigated in detail by surface and sub-surface investigations; and tracer studies were conducted in bore holes for the safety of the structure.

3. Field Tracer Techniques

Tracer Technique in civil engineering is employed generally to delineate seepage path and identification of its source for study of dam and canal seepage/ leakage of the dam, reservoir or canal and monitoring the dilution of tracers in the areas of leakage, thereby enabling the delineation of path of seepage and identification of its source. The tracer techniques can be employed by utilizing two methods viz. Single Well or Point Dilution Technique and Multi-well Techniques. A tracer test is conducted by introducing one or more chemicals (tracers) such as (Sodium fluorescein dye, Rhodamine-B; Tritium) into the groundwater and measuring their concentrations over some time period at various sampling points downstream from the tracer introduction point. It is desirable to determine the distribution of the tracer in space and time. The number of sampling points (boreholes) is necessarily limited, so test data consist of concentration-versus-time curves (breakthrough curves) obtained at each sampling point [11,13].

Figure 3. – Idealized Conceptualization of an Inter-Well Tracer Test [11]

Tracer concentration is measured using a Laboratory Fluorometer (Fig 4). These studies were also conducted to assess the efficiency of remedial measures after providing treatment at project sites. It is also an efficient technique to determine direction of flow and seepage velocity through porous medium.

Figure 4. Fluorometer

4. Tracer Test Design and Execution

Tracer tests are conducted to determine the transport properties (effective porosity and dispersivity) of rock. Ground-water velocity is inversely proportional to effective porosity. For fractured-rock aquifers, where porosities can vary greatly and be very small (10^{-3} , compared to 10^{-1} for unconsolidated deposits), tracers can move significantly more quickly than in unconsolidated deposits with a similar hydraulic conductivity.

A tracer test consists of introducing a tracer into rock and monitoring the tracer's movement and spreading. Natural-gradient tracer tests involve monitoring a tracer as it moves through the rock with ambient ground-water flow. Induced-gradient tests, such as those conducted for this study, typically involve creating a flow field with injection and (or) withdrawal, injecting a slug (pulse) of tracer in one well, and monitoring the arrival of the tracer at a second well. Dispersivity and effective porosity are determined from the shape and position of the time-concentration (breakthrough) curve.

Three-dimensional transport of a nonreactive solute in saturated porous media can be described by the following differential Equation (1) [12]:

$$\frac{\partial c}{\partial t} + v_i \frac{\partial c}{\partial x_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(D_{ij} \frac{\partial c}{\partial x_j} \right) \quad (1)$$

c is solute concentration

v_i is mean pore (solute) velocity in the x_i direction ($i=1,2,3$) and equals q_i/n [L/t]

q_i is Darcy velocity in the x_i direction [L/t]

n is effective porosity, and

D_{ij} is tensor of hydrodynamic dispersion, ($i,j=1,2,3$) [L^2/t]

Hydraulic and tracer tests are field methods for investigating fluid flow and chemical transport in the subsurface. They generally involve artificially inducing perturbations into the subsurface and measuring the resulting responses. In a hydraulic test the perturbation is created by injecting or withdrawing fluid from a borehole. The response is the change in fluid pressure in the same or nearby observation boreholes. In a tracer test a concentration perturbation is created by introducing a solute (tracer) into the subsurface. The movement of this solute is monitored by sampling for solute concentration at locations downstream from the tracer introduction point [11-14].

4.1 Estimation of Sodium Fluorescein in Test

The tracer mass required (M) was estimated by Equation (2).

$$M = 10 \cdot C_B \cdot V_W \quad (2)$$

where V_W is the water volume and C_B is the apparent background fluorescein concentration.

$$C_B \text{ (}\mu\text{g L}^{-1}\text{)} \text{ is equal to } C_B = 0.01 \cdot a \quad (3)$$

a varies with tracer fluorescence intensity ($a=1$ for sodium fluorescein).

4.2 Estimation of Tritium in Test

Tritium occurs naturally as reaction product between atmospheric nitrogen and thermal neutrons as per Equation (4):

It is a short-lived radioisotope, with half-life of 12.43 years used for young ground-water dating. The “effective age” is determined using the radioactive decay equation as per Equation (5), where A is the ground- water tritium activity measured at sampling time t , A_0 is the tritium activity at the time of recharge, and λ is the radioactive

decay constant:

$$A = A_0 e^{-\lambda t} \quad (5)$$

The limestone-test design at Narmada dam site was based on the assumption that the site contains limestone outcrops in the upstream of dam in the reservoir, in the foundation of dam; and in the downstream of dam. Faulting has displaced limestone rocks in the area necessitating appropriate location of bore holes on the limestone outcrops in the upstream and downstream and in the foundation of the dam considering its surface and sub-surface disposition.

5. Results and Discussions

In general, appreciable seepage was not observed in the foundation through basalt flows except at few locations where flow contacts were sheared and weathered. Seepage was observed through the contacts of infra-trappean sedimentary rocks during the excavation of treatment shafts and drifts. These rocks are present in the foundation of Right Bank blocks at shallow depth [16]. The limestone (30 to 60m thick) occurs in the foundation of spillway blocks 44 to 59 at about 40m depth (Fig 2). It was apprehended that limestone occurring in the reservoir as well as in the foundation of dam blocks might lead to the seepage and leakage of water from the reservoir. Therefore, extensive geological surface and sub-surface investigations were carried out to know the nature of the limestone.

Rock mass properties of limestone was explored by 14 exploratory drill holes down to depths ranging from 70 to 105m (El.15 to -95m). Rocks in the area are dissected by three sets of joints and associated with bedding shears. Joints are open on the surface and tight at depth. Cavities in limestone were not observed on surface nor in depth. However, drilling investigations revealed poor core recovery, high permeability and heavy water losses at few locations in limestone requiring tracer studies to ascertain the seepage path and to establish inter-connectivity of holes. Entire limestone area in the vicinity of dam was divided for conducting tracer studies into three parts: 1. Upstream of the Mokhadi fault, 2. In the foundation area below the dam base, and 3. In the downstream of the dam upto 225m from toe of the dam.

There is always permanent movement or normal seepage of the water after the construction of the dam from the reservoir under and around the dam and at the rims of the reservoir. If this movement or escape of water from the reservoir through the fissures and openings in the rock, buried channels etc. becomes abnormally large it is known as leakage (flow >125 Ltr./ minute/ 10m length) [19]. Fissures characteristics of the rocks at Narmada

dam site were investigated through pressure testing in drill holes and also by direct observations of foundation treatment shafts and drifts during their excavation [16]. Water pressure tests in the basalt were misleading as adjacent holes often gave entirely different permeability values. Natural cavities such as lava tunnels and caverns were not found present in the area. Presence of limestone in the reservoir, dam foundation and in the downstream area necessitated seepage analysis by Tracer studies to evaluate possibility of seepage losses through Limestone to provide treatment, if necessary.

Following are the results of tracer studies carried out for the limestone:

(i) Sodium Fluorescein and Tritium were injected in the drill holes located in the upstream of Mokhadi fault. Even after 15 days tracers were not observed in the boreholes located in the downstream of the fault.

(ii) Sodium Fluorescein was injected in the hole located 5m upstream of the dam axis. Average velocity of 20 to 30m per day was observed on the basis of observation in two bore holes located at 20m and 80m downstream, respectively. In another hole at 30m upstream of dam axis sodium chloride was used. No tracer was noticed even after 5 days in the observation holes located 5 and 60m away. Similarly, Tritium was used in other holes but no tracer of Tritium could be traced even after 8 days.

(iii) In view of high velocity observed in one of the section further Fluorescein studies were done in the area. Out of three observational bore hole, porous velocity 2.16×10^{-3} cm/ sec was observed in one of the holes. It might be due to presence of local permeable pocket.

(iv) Sodium Fluorescein was injected in a hole located at 225m downstream of the dam and observations were made in the drill holes located at 15, 18, and 120m away but no tracer was observed in the observation holes (Fig 5).

Figure 5 - Illustration showing a multi-well monitor network failing to intersect a plume either due to inadequate well spacing and a sinking plume [11] or due to cut off seepage path by geological features/ discontinuities.

6. Conclusions

The objective of study was to investigate the seepage characteristic of limestone by conducting detailed geotechnical and geohydrological investigations to identify interconnected permeable zones which may cause leakage of reservoir water through dam foundation. Surface mapping and sub-surface exploration during pre-construction and construction stage investigations have not revealed cavities in the limestone but high permeabilities were observed in a few drill holes. To rule out possibility of missing cavities and other permeable features between exploratory holes additional 14 drill holes down to entire depth of limestone were drilled for tracer studies. Analysis of tracer studies data could not establish neither cavities in the limestone nor interconnection between test holes. Thus, this study ruled out possibility of presence of cavities and continuous permeable zones. Moreover, chemical analysis of limestone revealed its siliceous nature (average SiO₂ 20%) and thus there was very less possibility of occurrence of chemical cavities. It corroborated tracer studies results. In some sections high permeability was observed in few drill holes, which might be due to the presence of local permeable pockets/ zones. These permeable pockets/zones were treated by increasing depth of curtain grouting down to depth of entire section of limestone below dam base.

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